

Grain yield of DJ.12519 and local Ikong Pao for drought-prone areas in Senegal. ^a

Variety	Yield (t/ha)					
	1981 (1029 mm, 80 d)		1982 (943.8 mm, 72 d)		1983 (769.2 mm, 71 d)	
	Djibélor	Diana-Bâ	Djibélor	Diana-Bâ	Djibélor	Diana-Bâ
DJ.12.519	3.6	4.1	4.3	5.1	1.3	2.9
Ikong Pao	3.4	3.0	2.2	3.8	0.3	1.3

^aValues in parentheses indicate rainfall (mm) and no. of rainy days.

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization ADVERSE SOILS TOLERANCE

Accumulation and distribution of Na and K ions in rice genotypes with different sodicity resistance

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In glycophytes, salinity or sodicity resistance is commonly correlated with the ability to restrict the entry of ions into the shoot. Rice is not known to possess much exclusion and selectivity at the root level, but some recent reports suggest that salt-resistant varieties are able to maintain younger leaves at lower Na concentrations under NaCl salinity. However, no information exists about such distribution patterns under sodic stress.

Sodicity-resistant CSR-1 and CSR-3 and sensitive Basmati 370 and M-1-48 were grown on sodic soils artificially prepared by adding NaHCO₃ to create pH 9.3, 9.5, 9.9, and a sodic soil of pH 8.1 which correspond to 35, 45, 72, and 8 exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP). Plants were grown in 17-kg-capacity porcelain pots. CSR-1 and CSR-3 are selections from local indicas, Basmati 370 is a local selection for long grain and aroma, and M-1-48 is used as a check.

Resistant varieties had better survival, establishment, growth, and yield. Sensitive varieties had seed sterility and grain filling problems even at moderate pH 9.5 and yielded nothing at the highest pH.

Na and K concentrations in younger green leaves, senescing yellow leaves, panicles, and stems of 4 rice varieties at grain filling stage, Karnal, India.

Plant growth and distribution patterns of Na and K were monitored. Sensitive varieties had reduced growth and yield, higher Na concentrations, and lower K concentrations in all plant organs (see figure). Resistant varieties showed better growth and yields, relatively lower increases in Na concentrations, and less K depletion. Highest Na concentrations under sodic conditions were in the following order: senescing yellow leaves > panicles > stem > young green leaves.

Very high Na concentrations accompanied by low K concentrations in sodicity-sensitive varieties appear to be the primary reason for their poor growth and yield ability. *S*

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